

SEMI-SYMMETRIC NON-METRIC CONNECTION ON COSYMPLECTIC MANIFOLD

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ABSTRACT

The main object of this research work is to study a semi-symmetric non-metric connection on Cosymplectic manifold and to demonstrate results based on the curvature tensor, Ricci tensor and scalar curvature with respect to semi-symmetric non-metric connection.

Keywords: Almost contact manifold, Cosymplectic manifold, η –Einstein manifold.

1. INTRODUCTION

Let \bar{D} be a linear connection in an n-dimensional differentiable manifold. The torsion tensor \bar{T} and the curvature tensor \bar{R} of \bar{D} are given by $\bar{T}(X, Y) = \bar{D}_X Y - \bar{D}_Y X - [X, Y]$ and $\bar{R}(X, Y)Z = \bar{D}_X \bar{D}_Y Z - \bar{D}_Y \bar{D}_X Z - \bar{D}_{[X, Y]} Z$. The connection \bar{D} is symmetric if its torsion tensor satisfies $\bar{T}(X, Y) = 0$, otherwise it is non-symmetric. The connection \bar{D} is metric if $(\bar{D}_X g)(Y, Z) = 0$, otherwise non-metric. It is well known that the linear connection is symmetric and metric if and only if it is a Riemannian connection. Hayden (1932) introduced a metric connection \bar{D} with non-zero torsion on the Riemannian manifold. Such a connection is called a Hayden connection. Weyl connection defined by Folland (1970) was a symmetric non-metric connection.

In 1924, Friedmann and Schouten introduced the concept of a semi-symmetric metric connection if its torsion tensor \bar{T} is of the form $\bar{T}(X, Y) = \eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y$, where η is a 1- form defined by $\eta(X) = g(X, \xi)$. A systematic study of the semi-symmetric metric connection on a Riemannian manifold was initiated by Yano (1970). Various types of semi-symmetric metric and non-metric connection were studied by many geometers such as Prasad and Verma (2004), Prasad and Singh (2006) and others.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Let M be an odd dimensional differentiable manifold on which there are defined a real vector valued linear function ϕ , 1-form η and a vector field ξ satisfying

$$\phi^2 X = -X + \eta(X)\xi \text{ and } \eta(\xi) = 1, \tag{2.1}$$

$$\phi\xi = 0; \eta(\phi X) = 0 \text{ and } \text{rank}(\phi) = n - 1, \tag{2.2}$$

for arbitrary vector fields X, Y and Z on M is called an almost contact manifold Sasaki (1965, 1966, 1968) and the structure (ϕ, ξ, η) is called an almost contact structure on M , Blair (1976). An almost contact manifold M on which there is a metric g satisfying

$$g(\phi X, \phi Y) = g(X, Y) - \eta(X)\eta(Y) \text{ and } g(X, \xi) = \eta(X), \tag{2.3}$$

is called an almost contact metric manifold and the structure (ϕ, ξ, η, g) is called an almost contact metric structure Blair (1976).

The product of an almost contact manifold M and the real line \mathbb{R} carries a natural almost complex structure. However if one takes M to be an almost contact metric manifold and suppose that the product metric G and $M \times \mathbb{R}$ is Kählerian, then the structure on M is Cosymplectic and not Sasakian.

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Let us put

$$F(X, Y) = g(\phi X, Y) = -g(X, \phi Y) = -F(Y, X). \quad (2.4)$$

Thus the tensor F is skew-symmetric i.e. $F(X, Y) + F(Y, X) = 0$.

An almost contact metric manifold M on which

$$D_X \phi = 0 \Leftrightarrow (D_X F)(Y, Z) = 0, \quad (2.5)$$

is said to be Cosymplectic manifold. Goldberg (1963) defined a Cosymplectic manifold on which

$$(D_X \phi)(Y) = 0 \text{ and } (D_X \eta)(Y) = 0. \quad (2.6)$$

But the second equation is not necessary because the first equation implies the second equation as follows:

$$(D_X F)(Y, Z) = 0 \Rightarrow (D_X F)(Y, \xi) = 0 \Rightarrow (D_X \eta)(Y) = 0.$$

It is easy to see that a Cosymplectic manifold is normal.

Definition 2.1: A Cosymplectic manifold (M, g) is said to be of quasi-constant curvature Yano and Ehen (1972) if the curvature tensor R of the Levi-Civita connection is given by

$$R(X, Y)Z = a\{g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y\} + b[\{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\}\eta(Z) + \{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\xi], \quad (2.7)$$

where a and b are scalar function. If $b = 0$, then the manifold is reduces to a manifold of constant curvature Kobayashi and Nomizu (1963).

Definition 2.2: A Cosymplectic manifold (M, g) is said to be an η -Einstein manifold if its Ricci tensor Ric is of the form

$$Ric(X, Y) = ag(X, Y) + b\eta(X)\eta(Y). \quad (2.8)$$

Definition 2.3: A Cosymplectic manifold (M, g) is said to be generalized η -Einstein manifold if its Ricci tensor Ric is of the form

$$Ric(X, Y) = ag(X, Y) + b\eta(X)\eta(Y) + cF(X, Y), \quad (2.9)$$

where a, b and c are scalar function and $F(X, Y) = g(\phi X, Y)$. In particular if $c = 0$, then generalized η -Einstein manifold reduces to η -Einstein manifold.

3. SEMI-SYMMETRIC NON-METRIC CONNECTION \bar{D}

A type of semi-symmetric non-metric connection \bar{D} is given by Siya Ram and Niraj Kumar Gupta (2022)

$$\bar{D}_X Y = D_X Y + a\eta(X)Y + b\eta(Y)X + c g(X, Y)\xi, \quad (3.1)$$

where a, b and c are non-zero real numbers and ξ is a vector field defined by $g(X, \xi) = \eta(X)$, for all X and Y on M .

From (3.1), the torsion tensor \bar{T} of manifold M with respect to the connection \bar{D} is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{T}(X, Y) &= \bar{D}_X Y - \bar{D}_Y X - [X, Y] \\ &\Rightarrow \bar{T}(X, Y) = (a - b)\{\eta(X)Y - \eta(Y)X\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

A linear connection whose torsion tensor satisfying (3.2) is called a semi-symmetric non-metric connection.

Further from (3.1), we have

$$(\bar{D}_X g)(Y, Z) = -2a\eta(X)g(Y, Z) - (b + c)\{\eta(Y)g(X, Z) + \eta(Z)g(X, Y)\}. \quad (3.3)$$

Hence a linear connection \bar{D} defined by (3.1) satisfying (3.2) and (3.3), we call a semi-symmetric non-metric connection. Particular case of this connection is given by Ram and Gupta in their paper (2022).

4. CURVATURE TENSOR, RICCI TENSOR AND SCALAR CURVATURE FOR SEMI-SYMMETRIC NON-METRIC CONNECTION \bar{D}

In this section we get the expression for the curvature tensor, Ricci tensor and scalar curvature with respect to semi-symmetric non-metric connection \bar{D} via (3.1).

Analogous to the definition of the curvature tensor R of manifold M with respect to Levi-Civita connection D , we define the curvature tensor \bar{R} of manifold M with respect to semi-symmetric non-metric connection \bar{D} is given by

$$\bar{R}(X, Y)Z = \bar{D}_X \bar{D}_Y Z - \bar{D}_Y \bar{D}_X Z - \bar{D}_{[X, Y]}Z \quad (4.1)$$

and

$$R(X, Y)Z = D_X D_Y Z - D_Y D_X Z - D_{[X, Y]}Z \quad (4.2)$$

is the curvature tensor of a Riemannian manifold M with respect Riemannian connection D .

From (3.1), (4.1) and (4.2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}(X, Y)Z &= R(X, Y)Z + a\{(D_X \eta)(Y) - (D_Y \eta)(X)\}Z + b\{(D_X \eta)(Z)Y - (D_Y \eta)(Z)X\} \\ &\quad + c\{g(Y, Z)(D_X \xi) - g(X, Z)(D_Y \xi)\} + b^2\{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\}\eta(Z) + c^2\{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) \\ &\quad - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\xi + bc\{g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y\}\eta(\xi). \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

Using (2.5) and (2.6) in (4.3), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}(X, Y)Z &= R(X, Y)Z + b^2\{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\}\eta(Z) + c^2\{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) \\ &\quad - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\xi + bc\{g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y\}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

Putting $Z = \xi$ in (4.4), we get

$$\bar{R}(X, Y)\xi = R(X, Y)\xi + b(b + c)\{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\}. \quad (4.5)$$

In the view of (4.4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}(X, Y, Z, W) &= 'R(X, Y, Z, W) + b^2\{\eta(Y)g(X, W) - \eta(X)g(Y, W)\}\eta(Z) \\ &\quad + c^2\{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\eta(W) + bc\{g(Y, Z)g(X, W) - g(X, Z)g(Y, W)\}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

where $'\bar{R}(X, Y, Z, W) = g(\bar{R}(X, Y, Z, W))$ and $'R(X, Y, Z, W) = g(R(X, Y, Z, W))$.

From (4.6), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}(X, Y, Z, W) + \bar{R}(Y, X, Z, W) &= b^2\{\eta(Y)g(X, W) - \eta(X)g(Y, W)\}\eta(Z) + c^2\{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) \\ &\quad - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\eta(W) + bc\{g(Y, Z)g(X, W) - g(X, Z)g(Y, W)\} + b^2\{\eta(X)g(Y, W) \\ &\quad - \eta(Y)g(X, W)\}\eta(Z) + c^2\{g(X, Z)\eta(Y) - g(Y, Z)\eta(X)\}\eta(W) + bc\{g(X, Z)g(Y, W) \\ &\quad - g(Y, Z)g(X, W)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging the above terms, we get

$$'R(X, Y, Z, W) + \bar{R}(Y, X, Z, W) = 0. \quad (4.7)$$

Again on proceeding in the same way, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}(X, Y, Z, W) + \bar{R}(X, Y, W, Z) &= (b^2 - c^2)[\{\eta(Y)g(X, W) - \eta(X)g(Y, W)\}\eta(Z) \\ &\quad + \{\eta(Y)g(X, Z) - \eta(X)g(Y, Z)\}\eta(W)]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}(X, Y, Z, W) - \bar{R}(Z, W, X, Y) &= b^2[\{\eta(Y)g(X, W) - \eta(X)g(Y, W)\}\eta(Z) \\ &\quad + \{\eta(W)g(Z, Y) - \eta(Z)g(W, Y)\}\eta(X)] + c^2[\{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\eta(W) \\ &\quad + \{g(W, X)\eta(Z) - g(Z, X)\eta(W)\}\eta(Y)] + 2bc\{g(Y, Z)g(X, W) - g(X, Z)g(Y, W)\}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

Similarly, we have

$$'R(X, Y, Z, W) + \bar{R}(Y, Z, X, W) + \bar{R}(Z, X, Y, W) = 0. \quad (4.10)$$

In the view of (4.6), (4.7), (4.8), (4.9) and (4.10), we have the following theorem:

Theorem 4.1: The curvature tensor \bar{R} of Cosymplectic manifold with respect to semi-symmetric non-metric connection \bar{D} satisfies the following:

- i. It is skew-symmetric in first two slots.
- ii. It is not skew-symmetric in last two slots *i.e.* $\bar{R}(X, Y, Z, W) + \bar{R}(X, Y, W, Z) \neq 0$ in general.
- iii. It is not symmetric in first pair and second pair of slots *i.e.* $\bar{R}(X, Y, Z, W) - \bar{R}(Z, W, X, Y) \neq 0$ in general.
- iv. It satisfies Bianchi's first identity.
- v. If a Cosymplectic manifold M admits a semi-symmetric non-metric connection \bar{D} whose curvature tensor is of the form $\bar{R}(X, Y)Z = (b^2 - c^2)\{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\}\eta(Z)$, then the manifold is of quasi constant curvature.
- vi. If a Cosymplectic manifold M admits a semi-symmetric non-metric connection \bar{D} , then curvature tensor $\bar{R}(X, Y)\xi$ of \bar{D} is equal to curvature tensor $R(X, Y)\xi$ of D if and only if $b(b + c)\{\eta(X)Y - \eta(Y)X\} = 0$ for weaker condition.

Let $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n: 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ be a local orthonormal basis of the tangent space at a point of the manifold. Then putting e_i for X and W in (4.6), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{R}(e_i, Y, Z, e_i) &= 'R(e_i, Y, Z, e_i) + b^2\{\eta(Y)g(e_i, e_i) - \eta(e_i)g(Y, e_i)\}\eta(Z) + c^2\{g(Y, Z)\eta(e_i) \\ &\quad - g(e_i, Z)\eta(Y)\}\eta(e_i) + bc\{g(Y, Z)g(e_i, e_i) - g(e_i, Z)g(Y, e_i)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Which gives on simplification

$$\bar{Ric}(Y, Z) = Ric(Y, Z) + \{(n - 1)bc + c^2\}g(Y, Z) + \{(n - 1)b^2 - c^2\}\eta(Y)\eta(Z). \quad (4.11)$$

Interchanging Y and Z in (4.11), we get

$$\bar{Ric}(Z, Y) = Ric(Z, Y) + \{(n - 1)bc + c^2\}g(Z, Y) + \{(n - 1)b^2 - c^2\}\eta(Y)\eta(Z). \quad (4.12)$$

On subtracting (4.12) from (4.11), we get

$$\bar{Ric}(Y, Z) - \bar{Ric}(Z, Y) = 0. \quad (4.13)$$

Putting ξ for Z in (4.11), we get

$$\bar{Ric}(Y, \xi) = Ric(Y, \xi) + (n - 1)\{b(b + c)\}\eta(Y). \quad (4.14)$$

Again contracting (4.11), we get

$$\bar{r} = r + (n - 1)(nbc + b^2 + c^2), \tag{4.15}$$

where \bar{Ric} and Ric are the Ricci tensor and \bar{r} and r are scalar curvature with respect to connection \bar{D} and D respectively i.e. $\bar{r} = \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{Ric}(e_i, e_i)$ and $r = \sum_{i=1}^n Ric(e_i, e_i)$.

Summing up the above discussion, we can state the following theorem:

Theorem 4.2: The Ricci tensor \bar{Ric} and scalar curvature \bar{r} of Cosymplectic manifold with \bar{D} satisfies the following:

- i. The Ricci tensor $\bar{Ric}(Y, Z)$ is given by (4.11).
- ii. If the $\bar{Ric}(Y, Z) = 0$, then from (4.11) Ricci tensor of Cosymplectic manifold with D becomes of η - Einstein manifold.
- iii. $\bar{Ric}(Y, \xi) = Ric(Y, \xi) + (n - 1)\{b(b + c)\}\eta(Y)$.
- iv. If a Cosymplectic manifold admits a semi-symmetric non-metric connection \bar{D} , then Ricci tensor of \bar{D} is symmetric.
- v. The scalar curvature of Cosymplectic manifold with respect to semi-symmetric non-metric connection \bar{D} is equal to the scalar curvature of the manifold with connection D if and only if $(nbc + b^2 + c^2) = 0$.

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